

Calculating Air-to-Air Threat Reactions

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Abstract – This paper establishes general equations to calculate threat reactions to air-to-air combat, by analyzing the performance of aircrafts and air-to-air missiles. It was possible to calculate the RMax, NEZ, Crank time, Notch Time, and the MAR. It also cites a software that was developed during the making of the article to automate the process of calculating threat reactions.

Keywords – Air Combat, Threat Reactions, Weapons Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the air combat, both the offensive counter air and defensive counter air fights may have air-to-air missiles. Unless both sides have the same aircrafts and weaponry, one of them will have a higher weapon range than the other. To counter this and avoid being shot down, aircrafts may have to perform threat reactions. Just because they don't have the required range to shot down an enemy fighter, it doesn't mean the aircraft can't press forward. The range between aircrafts that are flying towards each other and one of them can launch a missile that will destroy the other is called RMax. The defending aircraft can turn sideways and, because of its speed, the missile wouldn't be able to reach it, requiring the attacking aircraft to launch the missile closer. Depending on the range between the two aircrafts, the defending one may have to turn 180 degrees, as to avoid being shot down. And below a certain range, called No Escape Zone (NEZ), any shot missiles toward that aircraft will hit it. Due to this, the defending aircraft must know when to execute certain tactics to push even further into enemy territory while avoid being shot down.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. RMax

To calculate the RMax, it is required to know the missile timeout, speed, and the speed of the defending aircraft. Multiplying the timeout by the inverse of the sum of the speeds of the missile and the defending aircraft will return the maximum range at which a launched missile will impact an aircraft heading to its direction.

Fig. 1. Head on missile launch.

B. NEZ

To calculate the NEZ, the missile timeout should be multiplied by the inverse of the difference of speeds of the launched missile and the defending aircraft, returning the radius of the no escape zone. If by any chance the defending aircraft is faster than the launched missile, there is no NEZ.

Fig. 2. Missile launched at No Escape Zone.

C. Crank Time

If the defending aircraft has a radar, it can be a good tactic to flank the attacking aircraft, keeping it in the radar range. Performing a crank will decrease the required range to launch a missile, while allowing the defending aircraft to push further into enemy terrain and keep and to eye on the attacking aircraft in the radar. Because the attacking aircraft may still be closing in, it is necessary to know when to abort the crank manoeuvre (divert the flight trajectory 30° to the side) and execute a notch manoeuvre (fly perpendicular to the direction of the attacker).

Fig. 3. Crank manoeuvre.

To calculate the crank time, its necessary to calculate the position the attacking and defending aircrafts will be when the attacking aircraft has the required range to launch a missile that will hit the defending aircraft while its flanking.

The maximum time of executing the crank manoeuvre can be calculated by multiplying the distance between the initial and final position of the attacking aircraft and the inverse of its speed.

D. Notch Time

Once the crank time is over, the defending aircraft can beam the attacking aircraft instead of becoming cold. That can be done to give time to better equipped aircrafts to enter the arena without the defending aircraft being pushed back.

Fig. 4. Notch Manoeuvre.

The calculation is the same of the crank time, considering the initial position the position the defending aircraft should stop flanking and the final position the position the attacker could launch a missile that would hit the defending aircraft while its beaming the attacker.

After the notch time is over, the defending aircraft should execute a pump manoeuvre (fly in the same direction the attacking aircraft is flying).

E. Pump Distance

Instead of executing a crank or notch manoeuvre, the defending aircraft may opt to keep flying straight to its objective. In this case, it needs to calculate the Minimum Abort Range (MAR) at which, when performing a pump manoeuvre (180° turn), the attacker will still be outside the NEZ.

Fig. 5. Pump Manoeuvre.

To calculate the MAR, it must be taken into consideration the time it takes for the defending aircraft to perform a 180° turn, and how much the attacker gets closer in this period.

To calculate the time to make the turn, first its necessary to calculate the turn radius. The turn radius can be obtained by diving the square of the defending aircraft's speed by the horizontal component of it is normal.

Then, the turn distance can be calculated by multiplying the turn radius by PI.

Finally, the turn time can be calculated by multiplying the turn distance by the inverse of the defending aircraft's speed.

The decreased range between the defending aircraft and the attacker can be obtained by multiplying the time it takes the defending aircraft to make the turn by the inverse of the attacker's speed.

If the defending aircraft is slower than the attacker, it may be added to the MAR a distance to allow survival during a chase. This extra distance can be obtained by multiplying the extra time by the inverse of the difference of the speeds of the attacker and the defending aircraft.

III. RESULTS

To automate the process of calculating threat reactions and decrease the time it takes to perform the calculations, a software was developed to manage this process. The software, Knapp Threat Reactions, is currently available in the Microsoft

Store for Windows 10 and can be used with an aircraft and a missile library to create visual aids for the pilots, illustrated by the figure below.

Fig. 6. Example of threat reaction visual aid.

REFERENCES

- [1] KNAPP, J. M. S. Software. **Knapp Combat**, 2020.
- [2] KNAPP, J. M. S. Software. **Knapp Threat Reactions**, 2020.